

Advancing Sustainability and Circularity in the Automotive Industry: A Data-Driven Platform Approach

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Abstract—In the complex and rapidly evolving landscape of the automotive industry, sustainability and circularity are becoming increasingly crucial. However, the shift towards a Circular Economy (CE) is hindered by a multitude of barriers, especially by the limited collaboration between actors in the automotive value chain. A key challenge involves bridging the significant gap between Beginning-of-Life (BoL) and End-of-Life (EoL) actors in term of information sharing. The lack of open data exchange prevents, from one side, the optimization of End-of-Life Vehicle management processes, and from the other one, the enhancement of design practices oriented towards an easier disassembly and recycling of vehicles. Even in case data are available to decision-makers, their comprehension and elaboration process is not efficiently performed. To address these critical issues, an innovative web-based multi-layered data-driven platform has been developed, specifically designed to foster the communication and exchange of valuable and most of the time confidential information and knowledge along the automotive value chain. Integrating state-of-the-art analytics, tools, and user-friendly interfaces, the platform manages complex and disperse data and transforms them into actionable insights, facilitating informed decision-making and supporting the implementation of enhanced sustainable and circularity practices. This paper is meant to depict i. the software architecture, which follows a data-driven approach to guide the automotive sector transformation into a networked environment; and ii. the different software modules of the platform, highlighting their data requirements and interactional model. The initial validation of the platform has been conducted through a comprehensive survey within the automotive industry. Stakeholders' feedback on the platform's usability, functionality, and effectiveness in enhancing sustainability and circularity have been gathered and provided insights for further refinement. The development of the platform, thanks to its strategically designed architecture and functionalities, marks a significant step forward in the field of data management and decision-making in automotive sector. The validation results underscore the platform's potential as an indispensable tool to influence sustainable and circularity practices across the automotive value chain.

Keywords—Sustainability Platform, Data-driven Circularity, Circular Economy Platform, Circular Automotive

I. INTRODUCTION

Currently, one of the main challenges – and opportunity – that all companies are encountering is the integration of sustainability in their activities and the adoption of Circular Economy (CE) practices, which is a primary approach to improve sustainability [1]. This trend is supported by the European Commission through several initiatives, including extensive research projects and a series of regulations. These regulations range from setting general sustainability targets [2] to more specific focusing on the eco-design of products [3] and sustainability reporting requirements [4], highlighting that all the companies are affected.

The automotive industry, in particular, is increasingly influenced by evolving sustainability practices, and major car makers have embraced the use of environmentally friendly resources. For example, from 2021 to 2025, Ford plans to incorporate 20% sustainable materials in its vehicles [5]. Similarly, Volkswagen aims to halve carbon emissions per vehicle across all its plants [6], and Toyota aims to reduce the average carbon emissions of its new vehicles by 30% compared to 2010 [7]. Looking ahead to the 2026-2030 period, General Motors [8] is committed to using 100 per cent renewable energy for its US-manufactured vehicles and intends to reduce greenhouse gas emissions from its plants by 31%. In addition, several automakers, including Honda, Nissan, Toyota, Volvo and Volkswagen, are striving to achieve carbon neutrality between 2031 and 2050.

In the context of the CE, significant opportunities to improve sustainability and resource efficiency are present in both the Beginning-of-Life (BoL), implementing eco-design principles, such as Design for Recyclability (DfR) and Design for Disassembly (DfD), and in the End-of-Life (EoL) phases of a product's life cycle. However, the influence of product design on the efficiency of EoL processes emphasises that these phases are not isolated, but intrinsically interconnected. Therefore, bridging the substantial gap between BoL and EoL represents a crucial challenge.

Addressing this obstacle and implementing CE strategies in the automotive industry presents several hurdles. First, (i) there is a need for enhanced collaboration and information sharing along the value chain, from manufacturers to recyclers. This gap often prevents the transmission of essential information that is crucial for optimising the life cycle of vehicles, especially in the EoL phase, significantly hampering effective recycling and material reuse efforts [9]; (ii) technological and infrastructural limitations to achieve efficient material recovery, especially for complex components such as batteries in electric vehicles. Furthermore, the existing infrastructure is often insufficient to effectively manage end-of-life vehicles [10]; (iii) regulatory and economic barriers, as the adoption of EC practices is further complicated by the diversity of regulatory frameworks and the absence of adequate economic incentives in different regions. Discrepancies in waste management and recycling standards can hinder innovative approaches and discourage investment in technology [11].

To overcome these barriers, specifically (i), Supply Chain Collaboration (SCC) and enhanced information sharing have emerged as strategic approaches for companies to gain a competitive advantage in today's dynamic business environment [12]. SCC approach involves deeper coordination, shared information, and joint decision-making between supply chain partners, facilitating the ability to meet customer demands and improve profitability, something that hardly happens alone [13]. The dynamic challenges posed by

intense competition, complex market conditions and evolving regulations have increased the importance of effective information sharing within supply chains. Research by [14] highlights how collaborative activities can amplify the value generated along the supply chain. Furthermore, [15] emphasizes the positive impact of information sharing on annual profits, especially in sustainable supply chains where social and environmental costs are significant factors. Thus, SCC is crucial to foster innovation and support in achieving the main challenges that companies are facing.

Considering the automotive industry, the implementation of SCC strategies, to facilitate open data exchanges along the supply chain, is crucial to enhance the circular economy (CE) adoption from the beginning to the end of the life cycle. Such exchanges make it possible to optimise end-of-life vehicle management processes and improve design practices to facilitate dismantling and recycling of vehicles. Furthermore, it is essential to improve cooperation between all stakeholders in the automotive value chain. This can be achieved by creating platforms for sharing best practices and developing common frameworks to guide the implementation of CE initiatives.

These strategies suggest a multi-faceted approach involving technological innovation, enhanced collaboration, and supportive policies is essential for the automotive industry to overcome the current barriers to a successful CE implementation. These efforts are crucial not only for reducing environmental impact but also for ensuring the long-term sustainability of the automotive industry.

Several innovative tools and initiatives aim to improve information sharing along the automotive value chain. One prominent example is the Catena-X Automotive Network, designed to facilitate the seamless exchange of data between partners, thereby improving the sustainability and efficiency of the entire automotive supply chain. This network sets uniform standards for data and information exchange and is supported by a broad coalition of industry partners [16]. Another key tool involves the use of blockchain technology, as demonstrated by BMW with its PartChain initiative. This platform makes it possible to trace the origin of components between supply chain partners without the risk of data manipulation, ensuring transparency and trust between participants [17]. Both these systems, Chain-X and blockchain initiatives such as PartChain, provide structures for secure, standardised and efficient data sharing, which are crucial for optimising operations and improving collaboration at various stages of the automotive value chain. However, these tools that support the flow of information and offer significant value in the transition to CE approaches, do not explicitly support value chain with quantified KPIs, feedback and advice addressing the environmental, economic, and social sustainability of actors their day-to-day operations within the automotive industry.

This article seeks to address the challenges of the automotive industry focusing in particular on the life cycle management of Electronic Components (ECs) of a car. Specifically, an innovative data-driven platform, named Circularity Web Platform, specifically designed to improve the sustainability and to facilitate communication and collaboration between actors, promoting circular economy practices is presented. It serves to acquire, store, process and exchange information, involving actors in both the early life (BoL) and end of life (EoL) phases of products. Consisting of

three interconnected modules, Disassembly, Recycling and Eco-design, the platform optimises the sustainability and circularity performance of the ECs, supported by service and data layers for effective information management.

II. A DATA DRIVEN PLATFORM: APPROACH AND IMPLEMENTATION

The Circularity Web Platform (Platform from here on in the text) serves as a web-based multi-layered hub facilitating communication and collaboration among stakeholders of the automotive industry to promote circular economy (CE) practices. The Platform enables the acquisition, storage, processing and exchange of information among key actors of the automotive value chain, acting both in the EoL phase, i.e., dismantlers and recyclers, and in the BoL phase, i.e., designers, car makers and Tiers 1, 2 and 3. Best practices and recommendations are provided to the Platform users through key performance indicators (KPIs), e.g., disassembly metrics and recycling rates, supported by the expertise of material, recycling, and sustainability experts, aiming to optimize sustainability and circularity performance of the full value chain.

The Platform comprises three interconnected modules and related user interfaces. These three modules are strongly linked together, communicating information and feedback for the user in an interconnected manner:

- A Disassembly module, providing information on critical material content, disassembly metrics and instructions, and providing recommendations on most valuable car parts to be disassembled.
- A Recycling module, providing information on the recycling/recovery rates of car and electronics raw materials/elements/compounds (including losses and emissions) based on quantification of the recycling performance, and providing advice on best recycling routes and processes for optimal recovery and disassembly depth intensity.
- An Eco-design module, providing information on design feature and material content, and offering valuable indications for improving design based on recommendations derived from the disassembly and recycling module and sustainability metrics encompassing performance in a life cycle perspective.

The Platform modules and interfaces rely on two fundamental layers in order to retrieve the raw and elaborated data needed: the Service Layer and the Data layer, as in Fig.1 below. The Service Layer acts as middleware, hosting tools and services for decision support and facilitating interactions between the modules. Amongst the services it is worth of mentioning the Circular Advisory Tool that has been developed to provide intelligence to the system and equip the Platform with advisory functionalities. Each module is supported by the Circular Advisory Tool with specific functionalities that are meant to meet the requirements of each module user, generating advice to support sustainability and circularity-oriented, science-based decision-making. Specifically, the methodology establishes (i) what suggestions to give, to whom, and in what way; (ii) who can provide feedback, to whom, and in what format; (iii) how sustainability indicators, calculated by a sustainability assessment service integrated into the service layer briefly described in the following sections, are taken up and

transformed into suggestions. The Data layer manages data flow and storage, featuring components like the Data importer, for fetching external information and translating them in a standardized and suitable format for processing, and the Data Lake for centralized data storage and connection with Platform services.

The following section provides a detailed description of the technical architecture, highlighting the main technologies that are used for the developed Platform components.

A. Platform technical architecture

The Platform architecture can be divided into three sub-architectures, with the aim of providing categorized building blocks that exploit specific tasks at different levels of abstraction. The lower-level components are exploited by higher-level ones through a standardized interface that allows for generality of implementation and reusability throughout a wide variety of different scenarios. Fig. 1 shows how the individual components are grouped inside the three sub-architectures and a basic interactional model among them. For each layer, a dedicated paragraph describes its purpose in the Platform, the specific components that constitute it, and the integration with the rest of the Platform architecture.

Fig. 1. High-level Platform architecture.

1) Data Layer

Starting from the bottom, the first sub-architecture to be presented is the Data Layer, containing the components that heavily leverages data flow, storage, and manipulation. This layer constitutes the foundation for the main goal of the Platform, namely enabling the sharing of information among key actors in the automotive value chain. It is constituted by two main components, the Data Importer and the Data Lake.

a) Data Importer

The Data Importer is responsible for integrating with external data sources, both free and private ones, such as respectively RMIS, the EU database containing end-of-life vehicles volume and composition, and MISS database. The Data Importer provides the information coming from those sources to the Data Lake in a standardized format that is suitable for the processing operations to be performed. The Platform indeed relies on information coming from well-known CE data providers in order to enrich the amount of data at disposal of the various tools. This allows to have a more complete understanding about the impact of circular economy and circularity best practices in the automotive industry. To achieve this result, The Data Importer component is able to connect to designated external data sources through the usage of official dedicated APIs, to retrieve total or partial

information included in the data stores. Then, the Data Importer convert the retrieved information into suitable data types to be included in the Data Lake, depending on the format of data from the source and the target data stores.

b) Data Lake

The Data Lake stands as a centralized knowledge base, storing a variety of data coming from different tools, sources and actors. The component is also responsible for the making the data accessible to the rest of the Platform components, and through them, to the users. The stored knowledge is a combination of raw information from industry-standard external data sources, processed data and KPIs elaborated by different tools hosted in the Platform Service Layer, knowledge and recommendations provided by involved technical partners with expertise on materials, recycling and sustainability.

The main functionalities offered by the component are to: (i) provide data access to other Platform components by offering a standardized, query-based format to retrieve information; (ii) provide data access to end users either directly or by means of dedicated Platform tools; (iii) provide storage of data coming from other tools as output of their processes; (iv) provide storage of data coming from authorized users that decides to share relevant information with the rest of the Platform, contributing to enhance the overall available knowledge; (v) provide storage of aggregated data coming as a result of external assessments performed by external tools; (vi) regulate access of users depending on their role, organization and sensitivity level of information requested. This will be realized by the integration of the Platform with a RBAC (Role-Based Access Control) system, able to provide isolation of information and grant access to sensitive data only to the authorized users.

More in detail, the set of information contained in the Data Lake could encompasses: (i) car part chemical composition coming from external source, such as the already mentioned MISS database; (ii) augmented reality procedures, execution logs and user feedback, coming from a service similar to the WEAVR Platform one described in the Service Layer; (iii) information about car parts, components, materials and dismantling instructions, coming from BoL actors (cars/components manufacturers) and EoL actors (car parts/components disassemblers and dismantlers); (iv) environmental, social and economic indicators coming from a Sustainability Assessment Tool, leveraging external data sources, such as the ecoinvent database [18] and EoL actors (car parts / components shredders and components / materials recyclers); (v) recycling KPIs, materials composition and recycling routes for different disassembly depth coming from a Recycling Simulation Tool; (vi) disassembly information coming from the COBOT interface.

The actors whose actions are related with the flow of data through the Data Lake and their role with respect to the Data Lake are: (i) dismantlers, shredders and physical operators, who leverage knowledge from the Platform to carry out their designed tasks; (ii) car makers, components manufacturers and parts suppliers, who provide knowledge to the Platform by uploading car parts/components information into the centralized shared space; (iii) external data sources providers, who contribute to enlarge the content of the Data Lake by providing additional information about external data sources; (iv) recycling operators, who leverage the information available in the Data Lake to perform best recycling

procedures, according to relevant KPIs; (v) research and supportive partners, who provide different the data type mentioned above to be integrated in the Data Lake, contributing to enlarge the knowledge base available for other partners/tools; finally (vi) the user, who brings knowledge into the Platform by interacting with it.

To facilitate information flow, the Data Lake component has been also implemented with open standards, in order to allow future integrations with external systems that may leverage sustainability information coming from the current Data Lake knowledge. Indeed, the interaction among the Data Lake and the Platform services is realized by means of open APIs that allows the systems to communicate in a standardized way, ensuring reusability of the information sharing process and an easier and faster future improvement.

2) Service Layer

The Data Layer components is leveraged by the Service Layer to create the basic services contributing to the high-level platform modules. The Service Layer acts as a middleware and it is responsible for implementing the main components able to interact with multiple modules in different ways. Therefore, each individual component must be made serviceable for different purposes, depending on the upper layer it interacts with. This layer is meant to incorporate a set of tools that could support the automotive value chain in the journey toward a more sustainable and circular way to produce and close the product life cycle. Amongst the services that could be hosted by the layer the following ones can be mentioned: (i) a Recycling Simulation tool and a Sustainability Assessment tool, which provide suitable methodologies and algorithms that, starting from the raw data collected, allow to calculate recyclability, sustainability and circularity KPIs; (ii) a WEAVR platform [19], which supports operators in the physical dismantling procedures to be performed; (iii) an already mentioned Circular Advisory Tool, which supports the decision-making process that takes place in the three upper modules; (iv) a COBOT interface meant to allow the automatic dismantling of certain electronic car parts in order to enhance the material recovery capabilities; (v) a set of AWS Services [20] that supports all the behind-the-scenes tasks, such as user management, load balancing and data storage solutions.

The tools incorporated in the Platform are just an example of potential tools supporting automotive value chain through this Platform. Indeed, the Service layer is expandable to manage alternative software solutions for the same scopes and possibly in terms of supportive functionalities for future Platform versions.

3) Platform Modules

The last sub-architecture to be presented consists of the three main Platform Modules, each one focusing on a specific life cycle phase taking into account the needs of each specific automotive value chain actor involved. Each Module is composed by two main sections: the Dashboard, which provide a visualization interface showing key data and recommendations, and the Advisory, which provide an interactive interface where advice, generated through to the Circularity Advisory Tool and supporting tools, can be accessed. The Modules are hereafter described in terms of envisaged users and integration specific with the overall Platform.

a) Disassembly dashboard and advisory

The Disassembly Module (DIS) mainly address EoL actors, such as dismantlers and shredders. By combining the received information from car makers, car parts suppliers and external data sources, including for instance material composition, this module is able to provide information on critical and valuable car parts to be disassembled and generate valuable disassembly instructions.

Fig. 2. DIS module – Platform integration.

Fig. 2 shows the integration of the DIS with the Service Layer components and the Data Layer. The core of the DIS is represented by the Dashboard. This part of the Platform displays disassembly KPIs and metrics to the dismantling operators and can also be exploited by BOL actors, such as car makers. Through a dedicated form, the user is able to provide feedback concerning each specific step of the dismantling procedure. The feedback are then collected by the platform and inserted in the Data Lake for future usage. Additional information is then provided by the COBOT Interface. This component will record disassembly metrics regarding disassembly procedure from component to sub-components, such as dismantling time and information on feasibility of extracting sub-components from the main one. Further relevant information accessible through the dedicated Platform dashboard concerning the Circular Advisory Tool component, which helps the decision-making process by offering disassembly insight regarding material composition and cost, thermodynamic rarity of car components and different disassembly routes to choose from. Dismantling operator can also take advantage of the WEAVR Platform, which offers the ability to execute AR/VR dismantling procedures that allows EoL operators to speed up the dismantling process, while gain precious knowledge on which material and components are worth keeping and which ones have to be discarded. During the entire execution of the procedure, various metrics are collected from the WEAVR Platform All of this information is then stored in the Data Lake and serves as starting point for the Circular Advisory Tool to compute predictions and provide suggestions. Concerning the creation of the dismantling procedures, this is performed leveraging the disassembly instructions and CAD representation of the car parts/components provided by car makers and component manufacturers, as well as information present in the Data Lake and additional data coming from publicly available external data sources. These procedures also represent the main value that the DIS module brings, since they will be custom-built specifically to perform disassembly of car parts and components.

b) Recyclability dashboard and advisory

The Recyclability Module (REC) focuses on recycling procedures and sustainability KPIs obtained through the

Recycling Simulation tool and the Sustainability Assessment Tool. The REC mainly addresses recyclers, ranging from shredder, disassembler, and sorting plants to final treatment processing actors in the metallurgical recycling industry, in addition to car makers and designers.

The REC is applied to quantitatively assess the recycling or recovery of products and parts including all materials, elements and compounds applied in these. KPIs are generated to quantitatively assess recycling, for whole parts/product as well as for individual elements/materials, and energy recovery. In particular, the recycling/recovery rates (and losses/emissions created) for disassembled components/parts are calculated by application of the Recycling Simulation Tool. Most optimal balance between disassembly depth and best suited recycling flowsheet architectures are determined and the REC i.e., underlying simulation models, provide a physics and recycling technology-based feedback to Design for Recycling.

Fig. 3. REC module – Platform integration.

Fig. 3 shows the integration of the REC module with the Service Layer components and the Data Layer. The REC mainly leverages the Recycling Simulation Tool and the Sustainability Assessment Tool from the Service Layer.

The REC core contents are mainly provided by advanced recycling flowsheet simulation models, supplied by the Recycling Simulation tool and then technically implemented through the Recycling Application, leveraging on custom-built interactive procedures. Once data is collected into the Platform on detailed car parts compositional data, KPIs and the main recycling information (e.g., recycling/recovery rates, energy recovery, recycling routes to be followed for most optimal recycling,) is determined within the recycling simulation models. The process simulation model is performed by the application of rigorous and physics-based process simulation model such as the one performed by [22], [23]. The starting point of the recycling (and simulations) is to create material and metal products, alloys, compounds etc. of a functional quality so that these can be used in the same product these have originated from as this quality is required to achieve true circularity.

The recycling assessment, incorporating the full compositional detail of the car parts, recovered through metallurgical processing and energy recovery flowsheets and calculated recycling rates for the total car parts as well as all individual materials/elements provide the physics-based quantification to select most optimal processing routes, optimise Design for Recycling and make decisions and recommendations for more in depth disassembly.

Through the Sustainability Assessment Tool, such as the one described in [21], the Circular Advisory Tool supports the recycling processes by indicating the economic and social

impacts of the different recycling routes evaluated by the Recycling Simulation Tool, suggesting different ranking of these routes according to criteria such as recovery rate, environmental impacts, economic impacts, and social impacts generate by the recycling route.

The Platform leverages on the Recycling Dashboard to provide recyclers with valuable metrics for each car component, including material recycling routes for each optimization objective, material composition and individual recycling rates.

c) Eco-design dashboard and advisory

The Eco-Design Module (ECO) exploits the sustainability assessment tool to serve BoL actors, mainly designers, with proper knowledge generated by the Circular Advisory tool on top of the Platform data provided by the Data Lake. The Platform mainly acts as a recommendation system providing feedback collected from the DIS and REC. In particular, the suggestions collected from dismantling and recyclability assessments and feedback collected from the workers in the dedicated REC and DIS dashboards of the Platform, are recorded and made available in a proper collaborative space of the Platform, along with useful information on hardware components and sub-components, to identify critical parts in a vehicle, and valuable recommendations for the design phase based are provided to BoL actors.

Fig. 4. ECO module – platform integration.

Fig. 4 shows the integration of the ECO with the Service Layer components and the Data Layer. At the core of the ECO there is the ECO dashboard, which provides BoL actors (mainly car makers and component manufacturers) with interactive analytics and KPI specifications that allow them to better understand the current performance of their products. The ECO dashboard allows designers of electronic car parts and experts in materials and recycling to access and share information with an eye on developing novel prototyping processes and design alternatives. Currently, designers in the product development phase focus on functionality, cost and quality of the product, not considering the EoL of the product. The Circularity Advisory tool provides guidelines, suggestions, and assessments to designers to support them in creating a product designed to be disassembled and recycled in an optimized way. The selection of best design options is guided by offering the possibility to visualize EoL feedback for each car part/component provided by dismantling/recycling operators and the possibility to compare different KPIs in order to better understand which material/technical procedure is best suited for each use case. This is made possible by leveraging the Circular Advisory Tool for computing the appropriate KPIs based on the knowledge gathered from the Data Lake, and in collaboration with the Sustainability Assessment tool for the comparison of

environmental, economic and social KPIs between the actual design and possible alternative ones.

The platform leverages the AWS Services middleware to provide each actor with the appropriate visualization tool (e.g., producers of individual components only have access to KPIs and dashboards correlated to that specific part), ensuring security of critical assets and intellectual properties.

B. Platform functionalities, use case and sequence diagrams

As already stated, the Platform supports EoL and BoL actors in their day-to-day business to enhance the sustainability and circularity of their operations. In order to guide the design process of the Platform and to identify the main functionalities, use case diagrams and sequence diagrams has been depicted. Use-case diagrams are usually leveraged to representing the goals of interactions between actors and components of a system; defining and organizing functional requirements in a system; specifying the context and requirements of a system; modelling the basic flow of events in a use case. Considering three use case corresponding to the three modules of the Platform, the use case diagrams are reported in Fig. 5, 6 and 7.

Fig. 5. DIS use-case diagram.

Fig. 6. REC use-case diagram.

Fig. 7. ECO use-case diagram.

Sequence diagrams are usually developed to model high-level interaction between active objects in a system; model the interaction between object instances within a collaboration that realizes a use case; model the interaction between objects within a collaboration that realizes an operation; either model generic interactions (showing all possible paths through the interaction) or specific instances of an interaction (showing just one path through the interaction). Differently from use-case diagrams, sequence diagrams are developed with the user in mind, and in the context of the automotive value chain, they provide the interactional model behind each one of the three main platform modules from the point of view of the different groups of actors: Disassembly Operator, Recycling Operator and Car Maker. The sequence diagrams are reported in Fig. 8, 9, and 10.

Fig. 8. DIS user sequence diagram.

Fig. 9. REC user sequence diagram.

Fig. 10. ECO user sequence diagram.

Thanks to the analysis performed via the previous presented diagrams, the Platform design has been defined and presented hereinafter. From the home page of the UI, all modules and advisory are accessible to the user, as shown in Fig. 11. The shared section consists in the Home, Module application (Dashboard and Advisory) and Flowchart buttons; search bar to select a specific car component; user profile type. Three categories of users are available according to the granted authoring rights: (i) basic user, with visualization only mode and no authorization to edit; (ii) editor mode, for users that can add content on specific Platform sections; (iii) moderator mode, for users that can approve or reject data provided by the editor, leaving feedback in case of non-approval.

Fig. 11. Platform home page.

Considering the EoL phase, the DIS module (dashboard and advisory) provides the possibility to:

- Visualize information on material composition and economic value by material type classification and on disassembly metrics, such as time, cost, and difficulty (dashboard)
- Insert and display feedback for recyclers and designer (dashboard)
- Visualize critical metals composition, thermodynamic rarity [ref] and market value of the removed component at material level (advisory, as in Fig. 12)
- Estimate the priority of extraction according to the theoretical potential revenue originated from the recovery of materials embedded in the component (advisory, as in Fig. 12)
- Rank the electronic components in a car according to both their priority of extraction and their disassembly time (advisory, as in Fig. 12).

Fig. 12. DIS module – advisory user interface.

The REC module (dashboard and advisory) provides the possibility to:

- Visualize information on total and individual material recycling rates, energy recovery for the electronic component recycling (dashboard)
- Visualize the recommendation on most optimal recycling flowsheet infrastructure (dashboard)
- Insert and display feedback to BoL actors addressing design for recycling (dashboard)

- Rank the recycling routes based on recycling rates, environment, economic and social impacts (advisory, as in Fig. 13)
- Visualize a representation in the form of 3D chart that enables the user to understand at a glance the impact of selected disassembly and recycling routes in the three domains of sustainability (advisory, as in Fig. 13).

Fig. 13. REC module – advisory user interface.

Considering the BoL phase, the ECO module and related advisory provide the possibility to:

- Visualize the recommendations provided by EoL to improve design for disassembly and design for recycling (module)
- Examine compliance of existing design to specific guideline to enhance design for disassembly and design for recycling (advisory, as in Fig. 14)
- Prioritize design improvement actions (advisory, as in Fig. 14)
- Compare the performance of the current design with the one of an alternative design under the sustainability and circularity perspectives (advisory, as in Fig. 14).

Fig. 14. ECO module – advisory user interface.

III. PLATFORM VALIDATION

The final version of the technical specifications on which the Platform ultimate design and implementation is based is the result of a double validation process. The first one has been an internal validation. The list of the refined requirements emerged during the periodic discussion carried out within the consortium that designed and implemented the Platform, a group constituted by target users (car manufacturers and dismantlers), universities and research centres, IT firms. In addition to that, the integration and/or modification of the technical features takes into consideration not only the internal actors within this consortium but also external stakeholders to generalize the identified requirements. This process of external revision has been carried out to expand the list of additional users' needs to include in the identification of the platform specifications. The final goal is to ensure both internal and external validation to improve the solution adoption in different use cases depending on the involved stakeholder. The external validation process is reported in this section.

To expand Platform application and validation to actors outside the consortium, a survey has been elaborated to gain insights and feedback from a wide range of players in the automotive industry or cluster associations. The survey outcomes have been fundamental in the integration of technical requirements giving additional inputs that have been considered in the elaboration of the final version of the architecture. More in detail, the survey has been developed based on the following main goals: (i) clarifying the type of contents to incorporate in the Platform; (ii) acquiring, feedback on the methodological and technical features of the Platform; importing and structuring data within the data-lake of the Platform; (iii) opening the Platform to other users than the internal partners.

The effort was intended to enhance a broader stakeholder involvement in solution design and technical specification activities, by initiating open discussion of topics, aiming for a limited co-validation of platform functionalities.

The survey has been designed by the authors to include not only the feedback on the Platform but also on the methodology used for the Circular Advisory Tool definition. Thus, the questionnaire is structured in three sections: (i) Section 1 is dedicated to gathering general data from the interviewed actors in order to specify, cluster and analyse their contribution and have a better perspective in terms of value chain's covering; (ii) Section 2 is the methodological section (not presented in this work), where the interviewed actors are asked to select those methods and KPIs from the Circularity Advisory Tool that, from their personal perspective, will optimize the functionality of the Platform; (iii) Section 3 is the digital toolbox section where the interviewed partners are asked to provide useful suggestions on the selection of the most valuable functionalities to be embedded in the Platform in addition to pros and cons of the application value proposition.

A more detailed analysis of the results collected in each section and its related impact is provided in the following sub-sections.

A. Survey section 1: respondent general information

The goal of this section is firstly to provide an overview of project from which the Platform is resulted by describing its main objectives and secondly to collect general information

on the participant. This preliminary step is essential in determining the criteria for the results analysis since the questionnaire is open to a wide range of stakeholders coming from different professional backgrounds.

Overall, up to the moment when this document is released, a total amount of more than 50 respondents participated in the survey with an average time to complete of approximately 70 minutes. Most respondents belong to the private sector, more than half with respect to the public field (the replies classified as “Other” consist in Cluster organization and Innovation Cluster). Considering the professional background, the respondents mainly belong to clusters related to the automotive industry or more in general to mobility and technological innovation. The geographic composition shows a prevalence of European countries, especially Germany and Italy where the automotive sector plays an important role in the national economy.

B. Survey section 3: Platform

The last section of the survey is dedicated to the Platform in order to gain useful feedback on the application main functionalities, collect suggestions for technical improvements, determine the most appreciated distinguishing elements and possible barriers to adoption. The questions cover the whole platform to acquire a comprehensive knowledge of respondents’ opinion on key functionalities of each module and related advisory part. The section is split in three sub-sections corresponding to the three modules of the Platform. The same structure is used for all three applications:

- Platform demo. An explanation of the application goal, use and design/architecture is provided to ensure that participants were as much informed as possible on the Platform. This is made through a short video showing key platform features with a description of each requirement.
- Technical feedback questions. First set of questions are dedicated to the platform specifications from a technical point of view. Only relevant must-have requirements were selected from the full list of identified specs. The respondent is provided with a list of key technical specifications he/she can rate from No priority, through Low, Medium, High till Top priority. For each requirement the interviewee can provide a comment, feedback or suggestion on the specific item assessing which features are preferable. Then, it is asked for additional features considered useful/necessary that should/could be implemented to improve platform value.
- Business perspective questions. Last questions consider users’ feedback from a perspective focused on exploitation. The goal is to assess the respondents’ impressions about the Platform based on the key functionalities presented in the previous questionnaire sub-section. The first question investigates the recipients’ willing to pay for using the platform, and, if confirmed, the preferable buying option, between a pay per use solution and a subscription fee. Secondly, the survey recipients have to determine the most valuable and distinguishing elements of the platform for their potential use among a selected group of features. The last question of the survey was dedicated to the identification of the main barriers that could

prevent the Platform adoption, spanning from technical reasons to financial ones.

All respondents fully completed the survey answering all questions. The main results are reported hereafter:

a) DIS Technical feedback

From a requirements perspective, the highest priority has been given to that Platform features related to data provision, in particular to the sharing of materials composition and market value, disassembly time and costs, and to the calculation of the profit margin based on the ratio between the thermodynamic rarity indicator and the desired revenue value. The outcomes of these responses confirm the interest of stakeholder in accessing information perceived as critical to drive day to day operations and business strategy.

When asked about their preferences on additional functionalities, respondents pointed out an interest for accessing further data on specific material or part of the car component, i.e. disassembly instructions and re-use value of the component, and a range or “confidence score” for cost and profitability, which are time specific.

b) DIS Business perspective

Given the collected feedback presented, it is not surprising that, when asked if they would buy the platform, users’ answer is divided in two opposite results: 55% of them is in favour of paying to use the digital solution while the remaining 45% is not interested. It is interesting to note that, in the first case, the preferred buying option is in form of a subscription fee and not as per use. This implies that users are more interested in a long-term business relationship, not limited to a specific random use but as a continuous service to be exploited in day-to-day operations planning.

When asked to rank key functionalities/aspects of the Platform, the higher rating is assigned to the possibility to access strategic data (reinforcing the results of the first question on requirements prioritization) not only on material composition of car part but also on the disassembly procedures. The most valuable feature in fact is considered the support for the decision-making process leading to an improvement in efficiency of the dismantling operations planning.

When asked about possible limits in platform adoption, the financial element (i.e., additional cost/investment that is perceived as accessory or not strategic) counted the most (41 out of 116 replies), although no hints on the estimated price are intentionally given since the fee may consistently vary based on the use and additional services required. Moreover, technical integration in the business-as-usual solution is perceived as critical and must be taken into account for further development.

c) REC Technical feedback

Similarly to the Disassembly sub-section, also in this case the provision of data concerning materials composition is considered valuable, as well as the sharing of recycling rates from recycling simulations. Instead, environmental, social and economic dimensions do not play the same degree of relevance as the recycling rate visualization, according to recipients.

When asked about their preferences on additional functionalities, the respondents pointed out an interest for accessing further data on specific material or more details on

the energy recovery level to assist in better recyclability assessments. The comments concern also the parameters used for the recyclability analysis, proposing a comparison with standard recycling rate of the same product, which however is not implementable due to the difficulty in identifying a benchmark applicable for all use cases. A key feature that was pointed out and was in-line with the work done is the provision of feedback collected in the REC as recommendations on the most efficient and environmentally friendly (considering the best available technologies). These recommendation affects not only recycling but also the Eco-Design application functionality.

d) REC Business perspective

A lower percentage of respondents (53%) with respect to DIS would be willing to pay to exploit it. This could be related to the nature of the module, mainly presenting information and not providing suggestions or instructions on the specific application of recycling procedures. The preferred option for platform use is the subscription fee solution as in previous case.

When asked to rank key functionalities/aspects of the Platform, the higher rating is assigned to the support for the decision-making process leading to an improvement in efficiency of the recycling operations performance, especially to the opportunity to compare different metrics obtain in recycling simulations.

When asked about possible limits in platform adoption, also in this case the financial aspects counted the most (40 out of 109 replies). The second most voted limitation concerns the perception of the module as not aligned/relevant with company scope/business. This could be due to the respondents' professional background that does not match the recycling one.

e) ECO Technical feedback

Major interest of recipients is on the features that provide intelligence to the module and data provision. As already noted, the functionality related to the provision of recommendations and collection of feedback is considered valuable especially in this module, since car designer can have the opportunity to access knowledge coming from EoL actors to shape the BoL perspective.

When asked about their preferences on additional functionalities, respondents pointed out an interest for accessing further data on specific material or part of the car component (e.g., metallurgical incompatibilities and quantitative data on material recoveries and losses to improve the identification of possible alternative designs or facilitate comparisons. Moreover, recipients request additional explanation on indicators and data use to enhance transparency and system explainability. The feedback has been addressed through the insertion of informative pop ups.

f) ECO Business perspective

Half the respondents said that they would not be interested in purchasing the ECO. This could depend on the interviewees' professional provenience and the business field they operate in, and on the fact that this module mainly needs improvements in the implementation. In fact, with respect to the other two modules, ECO and more precisely the advisory part, has been shown in the alpha version, without the additional features and requirements beta and final version of

the platform. Also in this case, the preferred buying option is in form of a subscription fee.

When asked to rank key functionalities/aspects of the Platform, it is not surprising that the higher rating is assigned to the support in the decision-making process since it is the main goal of the ECO. It is interesting to note that the other options (such as: gain access to several relevant aggregated information; efficiency improvement for eco design performance; compare different key metrics) received almost the same ranking indicating that the application is versatile.

When asked about possible limits in platform adoption, the financial element is confirmed as the most impacting barrier as already noted for the other two modules. As previously pointed out, the answers need to be contextualized as the ECO is the most impacted by the revision made for the second version of the platform.

The answers collected from this survey play an important role in the refinement of the platform from multiple perspectives, including technical requirements, user support and exploitation strategy. The survey is available at the link: external stakeholder survey.

IV. CONCLUSION

The paper presented a critical advancement in the automotive industry's approach to CE practices, addressing the urgent need for improved data sharing and collaboration across the automotive value chain. The development of the Circularity Web Platform represents a significant step forward in bridging the information gap between the BoL and EoL stages that has historically hindered sustainable and circular practices in automotive manufacturing and recycling processes.

The Platform's innovative, multi-layered, data-driven architecture has proven effective in facilitating the flow of critical and often confidential information between stakeholders. By implementing state-of-the-art analytics and user-friendly interfaces, the Platform enables complex data management and transforms it into actionable insights for the involved actors, which can have a bird's-eye view of the circularity status of their current products, i.e., car ECs, in a single place on dedicated web pages. Charts, graphs, and visual tools are populated with critical metrics describing disassembly, recycling, design performances. The feedback mechanism, through textual recommendations and indicators addressing recovery rates, advice on material compatibility, suggestions on optimal disassembly depth and insights on modularity approaches to design, allows BoL actors to understand how design can contribute to meet the EoL requirements. This supports informed decision-making and promotes the implementation of improved sustainability and circularity practices throughout the value chain.

Initial validation through a comprehensive expert survey indicates a positive reception from stakeholders, confirming the Platform's functionality, usability, and effectiveness in improving circularity outcomes. The insights gained have helped to refine the platform to ensure that the Platform meets the dynamic needs of the industry, while pushing the boundaries of technological innovation in data management and decision support.

Considering future work, further validation activities will be carried out with key industrial partners through the actual testing of the Platform. Future validation and testing activities

will be aimed at expanding the collected intelligence to move from the presented knowledge-based expert system approach to the implementation of machine learning approaches in the Platform logic. The author suggest that continued development and refinement of the Platform will be crucial. Improving interoperability with existing and emerging technologies, increasing user engagement through intuitive design, and expanding the Platform's capabilities to cover broader aspects of CE will ensure that it remains a supportive tool for the automotive industry.

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